

Organizational Culture Adaptation to Flexible Work Patterns: HR Management Perspectives at Ultima Asia Network

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The digital revolution has transformed work patterns from the conventional 9-to-5 model to more flexible, giving employees freedom in time and place of work. This research focuses on the adaptation of organizational culture in Ultima Asia Network, a company in the digital and creative field that faces the challenge of decentralizing work. Through a case study approach, in-depth interviews, and participatory observations, this study explores how corporate cultural values are maintained and adapted to remain relevant in flexible working patterns. The results of the study confirm that the success of cultural adaptation is highly dependent on the strategic role of human resource management and the effective use of internal rituals to maintain innovation, collaboration, and the sustainability of a resilient and adaptive organizational culture.

INTRODUCTION

The digital revolution has given birth to a new way of working. The concept of conventional 9-to-5 working hours is slowly being displaced by flexible work patterns that offer freedom in time and workplace settings. This phenomenon not only has an impact on the organization's operational system, but also demands an adjustment in organizational culture and human resource (HR) management. Ultima Asia Network, as a company engaged in the digital and creative fields, is a concrete example of how business entities must adapt to an increasingly dynamic work landscape. Research by (Anhar et al., 2025) notes that "flexible working hours allow employees to work more efficiently at a convenient time and place, while work-life balance reduces stress, increases motivation, and boosts productivity" is particularly relevant for dynamic cultures such as those at Ultima Asia Network.

A strong organizational culture has been synonymous with physical work routines, face-to-face, and direct interaction between individuals. However, flexible working models challenge that paradigm by presenting significant physical distance. In this context, the role of HR management is crucial in building, maintaining, and adjusting organizational cultural values to stay alive in the midst of a decentralized work pattern. This study tries to explore how organizational culture adaptation in Ultima Asia Network is applied in support of a flexible work system, as well as how HR management plays a strategic role in the adaptation process. Research by (Musfira et al., 2025) highlights that "the Work From Anywhere organizational culture is shaped through technology-based adaptive communication and customized internal rituals, keeping values alive despite the separation distances" — this is particularly relevant to the culture adaptation strategy at Ultima Asia Network.

THEORETICAL STUDIES

Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is a system of values, beliefs, norms, and habits that develops in an organization and becomes a code of behavior for its members. This culture reflects the "way of working" of an organization that sets it apart from others. In the context of flexible working, organizational culture needs to accommodate the need for autonomy, trust, and measurable work outcomes. Research by (Zirho & Setiawan, 2024) confirms that "trust in the organization mediates the relationship between organizational culture and employee engagement", so that when work flexibility is enforced, strengthening trust is the key to keeping the organizational culture alive and employees staying engaged upstream, but it has a great impact on the downstream in the form of real performance.

HR Management

HR management is a strategic process in managing an organization's human assets, including recruitment, development, performance appraisal, and retention. In the midst of a flexible work pattern, HR management is required to be more adaptive in terms of communication, empowerment, and maintaining employee engagement. As found in the research by (Setyoningtyas & Febriansyah, 2024) "the flexible work system has a significant positive impact on employee engagement, especially among Millennials and Generation Z, and its effectiveness is strengthened by inspirational transformational leadership" is particularly relevant for Ultima Asia Network which emphasizes empowerment and adaptive communication through its human resources.

Flexible Work

Flexible work patterns refer to work systems that are not tied to a specific time and place of work. These models include remote, hybrid, or non-rigid work hours. Research by (Suyatno et al., 2023) shows that Flexible Working Space has a positive impact on work productivity, but its effectiveness is highly dependent on the character of the organizational culture that underlies the system, meaning that, without a strong and supportive organizational culture, flexibility can even weaken the internal attachment and cohesiveness of the organization.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach with the aim of understanding in depth the phenomenon of organizational cultural adaptation from the internal perspective of Ultima Asia Network. This approach is relevant because it is in line with similar studies, such as the research of Khaldun et al. (2025) which shows the importance of a collaborative and flexible work culture for employee well-being and productivity in the creative economy sector.

The research design used is a case study with a main focus on the Ultima Asia Network. Data collection was carried out through in-depth interviews with employees, especially freelancers, as well as participatory observation. This design is supported by the findings of Gerson et al. (2025) which affirm that case studies and in-depth interviews are highly effective for digging into insights into employee engagement and adaptive strategies emerging from within the organization. This research was conducted on Ultima Asia Network with the research subjects consisting of 5 *freelancers* and 3 permanent employees involved in cross-team projects. This approach is in line with the methodological practice of the study of Satria et al. (2025) which also compared the experiences of permanent and flexible employees to explore their perceptions of different aspects of work.

Data Analysis and Validity Techniques

Data analysis is carried out systematically through four stages. First, the transcription of data from the interview results is carried out verbatim to ensure the integrity of the information. Second, the data is thematically codified based on key topics such as communication, motivation, and cultural values. Third, similar codes are grouped into major themes, such as "open communication" and "cross-team collaboration". Finally, each theme is interpreted in depth to understand the context and meaning behind it.

To ensure the validity of the data, this study uses a triangulation technique. The triangulation method is applied to three aspects: source (comparing the views of permanent and *freelance* employees), method (combining interviews and observations), and member *checking* (validating interpretation with respondents). This approach is based on the theoretical foundation of Mekarisce (2020) which emphasizes that triangulation and *member checking* are fundamental to increase the credibility and confirmability of findings in qualitative research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The organizational culture at Ultima Asia Network is characterized as progressive, open, and collaborative, with upholding the values of trust, innovation, and results. The HR management approach applied focuses on employee empowerment, which is realized through work flexibility, clarity of project objectives, and a humanist approach. This culture is in line with the findings of Yunanda et al. (2025), who underline that an organizational culture that supports effective collaboration can spark innovation and improve performance.

This culture has a significant influence on employee performance, especially freelancers. First, work motivation and innovation increase because the flexibility of time given makes them have a high *sense of ownership* of their work. This is in line with research by Riyono & Usman (2022) which shows that *freelancers* are motivated by intrinsic factors, such as freedom and flexibility, rather than purely financial rewards. Second, open communication and collaboration run more fluidly through digital platforms such as Slack and Notion. However, Nisa's study (2024) reminds that although this horizontal communication is refreshing, minimal face-to-face interaction can potentially reduce the quality of interpersonal relationships if not balanced with effective strategies.

Meskipun dinamika budaya organisasi ini membuat para *freelancer* merasa menjadi bagian dari tim, tantangan muncul dalam hal keterikatan emosional terhadap organisasi. Studi Sadida & Febriani (2016) menemukan bahwa fleksibilitas dapat membangun *engagement* tinggi, tetapi absensi interaksi fisik dan struktur kepemimpinan yang longgar bisa membuat kedekatan emosional menjadi "jauh".

Implications and Recommendations

These findings carry important implications for HR management. Organizations need to develop a robust digital *onboarding* program to instill cultural values from the start, as well as implement results-based performance evaluations.

To overcome the existing challenges, it is recommended that Ultima Asia Network establish digital rituals, such as *weekly sharing* or *virtual townhalls*, to maintain an emotional connection between individuals. Meanwhile, for further research, it is recommended to conduct a comparative study between *remote* and *hybrid work cultures* in organizations with different hierarchical structures.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on research conducted at Ultima Asia Network, it can be concluded that a progressive, open, and collaborative organizational culture has successfully adapted to flexible work patterns. This success is supported by an HR management approach that focuses on employee empowerment, which ultimately increases motivation, innovation, and a sense of belonging, especially among *freelancers*. However, the main challenge that arises is maintaining employees' emotional attachment to the organization due to the lack of physical interaction. This suggests that flexibility, while increasing *engagement*, can make emotional relationships "distant" if not managed properly.

Suggestion

To address these challenges and strengthen organizational culture, the study recommends the following:

For Ultima Asia Network: HR management needs to develop a robust digital onboarding program and implement results-based performance evaluations. Additionally, it's important to establish "digital rituals" such as weekly sharing sessions or virtual townhalls to maintain an emotional connection between teams.

For Further Research: It is recommended to conduct a comparative study. The study could compare remote work cultures with hybrid in different types of organizations, especially those with different hierarchical structures, to gain broader insights.

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